

What Supports do Teachers Need for Effective Learning Designs while Integrating Technology? A Mixed Methods Study

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Abstract— Learning designs (LDs) involve intentional and systematic planning of learning experiences and activities to achieve specific educational goals. Creating effective learning designs is a complex task for school teachers, because they encounter various challenges that impact successful integration of technology in the classroom. Previous solutions such as teachers' training programs & workshops, online portals for sharing best practices, teaching frameworks & guidelines and learning design frameworks & tools have been developed to address this issue. However, these solutions have been reported to be insufficient in improving teachers' ability to design effective LDs. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the needs and supports that teachers required for learning design. This paper explores the supports that school teachers required for designing effective LDs and also investigate how teachers' demographics and background or context affect LD support required by teachers. We adopted a mixed research with 203 teachers from different schools in Delhi, India. Our results show that teachers need learning design support for creation, contextualization and collaboration. This study also suggests significant differences in teachers' support required for learning design according to the use of technology in the classroom and availability of computer at teachers' home.

Keywords— Learning Design, ICT integration, lesson planning, teacher education, learning design tool, teacher needs.

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic sparked a significant 'shift to digital' in school education due to the widespread adoption of online remote teaching [1]. This has brought online teaching and digital technologies to the forefront of educational practice and opened the door for future innovation, change, as well as concerns about how we teach and learn. This has led to a growing emphasis on the integration of technology and student-centered approaches in education. However, school teachers have reported to have difficulty in integrating information and communication technology (ICT) in the classroom [2]. This is mainly due to challenges in designing effective learning designs (LDs) with ICT integration in the classroom.

A widely cited definition of LD is provided by Conole, which states that learning design "involves designing the teaching and learning process, including the use of both pedagogical and technological approaches, to create an effective learning experience"[3]. This definition emphasizes the importance of integrating pedagogical principles with the effective use of technology to enhance the learning experience. LDs involve carefully selecting and sequencing instructional strategies, resources, assessments, and learning environments to support student engagement, understanding, and skill development. Effective LDs promote student

engagement, motivation, and meaningful learning experiences. They provide a structured framework for organizing instructional materials, activities, and assessments to support student learning outcomes. By incorporating pedagogical strategies, technology integration, and diverse learning resources, effective LDs cater to the needs and interests of students, facilitating more profound understanding and knowledge retention. Research suggests that well-designed LD can significantly enhance student achievement and academic performance [4]. When teachers utilize effective LDs, students are more likely to develop critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and creativity, essential for success in the 21st century.

Designing effective LDs that leverage technology and promote student engagement is a complex task that requires pedagogical expertise, technological proficiency, and a deep understanding of student needs [5]. Teachers play a pivotal role in this process, as they are responsible for designing LDs that foster meaningful interactions, cater to diverse learner needs, and facilitate the acquisition of knowledge & skills. Thus supporting teachers in designing effective LDs has become a significant area of research and development.

Various strategies and interventions have been implemented to assist teachers in representing their teaching ideas and adopting student-centered LD practices. These efforts aim to enhance the quality of education and promote more engaging and meaningful learning environments. One such approach involves the use of learning design tools that provide guidance and support throughout the design process [6]. These tools offer frameworks, templates, and resources that can assist teachers in structuring their learning activities and aligning them with intended learning outcomes. Training programs and workshops have also been employed to enhance teachers' understanding and skills in learning design [7]. These initiatives provide opportunities for teachers to learn about pedagogical theories, instructional strategies, and effective use of technology in designing student-centered learning experiences. Community-based platforms have emerged as another avenue for teachers to share knowledge, exchange ideas, and collaborate on learning design [8]. These platforms create spaces for educators to engage in discussions, access resources, and learn from each other's experiences, fostering a sense of community and professional development.

Despite these efforts, teachers' still do not adopt LD tools as expected. Existing efforts have been reported to be insufficient in improving teachers' ability to design effective LDs [9]. Teachers find it difficult to translate theory into practice [10] or customize best practices for their own context [11]. In addition, researchers have highlighted barriers such as lack of awareness or familiarity with student-centered

approaches, resistance to change, institutional constraints, and limited support or incentives for implementing innovative design practices [12] [13] [8]. Additionally, challenges related to time constraints, workload, and the complexity of integrating technology into design processes may also hinder the adoption of student-centered LD practices. Research also suggests that many teachers encounter obstacles in designing and implementing student-centered LDs [1]. These challenges often stem from a lack of adequate support that can assist teachers in navigating the complexities of integrating technology into their instructional practices. To address this gap, it becomes crucial to explore and identify the specific support requirements that Indian teachers need to effectively design LDs.

This study aims to delve into supports required by teachers in India for creating effective LDs. It utilizes a mixed-method approach, starting with in-depth qualitative interviews (N=6), followed by a quantitative survey (N=197) to examine the types of support teachers require for designing effective LDs while integrating ICT in the classroom. Additionally, the study aims to analyze how teachers' demographics and contextual variables may impact the required LD support. By understanding these needs, we aim to provide insights that can inform the development of targeted support for teachers to create effective learning designs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on student-centered learning and the integration of technology in educational practices. This shift has presented both opportunities and challenges for teachers, who are tasked with designing effective LDs that harness the potential of technology while catering to diverse learner needs.

A. *Effective Learning Design*

Learning designs provide a framework for teachers to structure and organize their teaching, ensuring alignment between learning objectives, content delivery, and assessment methods [10]. The concept of LDs recognizes the importance of considering various factors, such as the needs and abilities of learners, the subject matter, the learning context, the available resources, desired learning outcomes, pedagogical approaches, and available technologies, to create an engaging and meaningful learning. It encourages educators to design learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles, promote active participation, foster critical thinking, and support acquiring knowledge and skills. Educators can create cohesive and coherent learning experiences by employing LDs beyond merely transmitting the information. They focus on engaging learners in meaningful tasks, collaborative activities, problem-solving exercises, and authentic assessments that promote deep understanding and application of knowledge [14]

Designing LDs that focus on the needs, interests, and abilities of learners is crucial for effectiveness. This includes incorporating active learning strategies, promoting student engagement, and providing opportunities for student choice and autonomy [15]. Clearly defining learning goals and objectives helps students understand what is expected of them and guides the instructional design process. Learning goals should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound [16]. Connecting learning to authentic and real-world contexts enhances relevance and meaning for students. Designing learning experiences that reflect real-life scenarios

and challenges helps students see the practical application of their learning [17]. Incorporating ongoing assessment and timely feedback into learning designs supports student progress and informs instructional decisions. Various assessment strategies, such as formative assessments, self-assessments, and peer assessments, contribute to the effectiveness of the learning process. Integrating appropriate technology tools and resources can enhance the effectiveness of learning designs. Technology can support collaboration, provide access to information and resources, and facilitate interactive and multimedia-rich learning experiences.

B. *Existing Support for Teachers*

Previous research has highlighted the importance of various forms of support, such as professional development programs, collaborative communities, mentoring, and access to resources and tools [18].

Professional development programs play a significant role in supporting teachers' LD practices. These programs can provide teachers with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively integrate technology into their LD practices [19]. Professional development programs can provide training, workshops, and resources to support teachers in understanding and implementing effective LDs [20]. This supports included troubleshooting, training on specific technologies, and guidance on selecting appropriate digital tools for LDs.

Collaborative communities, such as professional learning networks & communities of practice, offer opportunities for teachers to share ideas, collaborate, and receive peer feedback thus enhancing their LD capabilities [8]. Collaboration & collegial support are crucial for teachers in implementing LDs. Collaborative environments provide opportunities for reflection, problem-solving, and the sharing of best practices. Mentoring has also been recognized as an effective form of support for teachers in LD. Mentors can provide guidance, feedback, and personalized support to teachers, fostering their professional growth and confidence in designing effective LD.

Furthermore, access to appropriate resources, such as learning design frameworks, technology tools, and instructional materials, is crucial in supporting teachers' design practices. Teachers require access to high-quality curriculum materials and resources that align with the learning designs they intend to implement. This support can include curriculum guidelines, instructional materials, and digital resources that support active learning, differentiation, and engagement. School administrators play a vital role in supporting teachers' implementation of learning designs. This support includes providing time for collaboration and professional development, allocating resources and funding, and creating a supportive school culture that values and encourages innovative teaching practices.

A study conducted by Bennett et.al to explore the support that assists university teachers in their design processes. They identified several crucial influences on design decisions, including teachers' perceptions of student characteristics, their own beliefs and experiences about teaching & learning, and contextual factors. Also, suggested various supports to improve design practices. These included enhancing teachers' knowledge of students, facilitating the sharing of practices, providing guidance on pedagogical theory, and enabling flexibility in design processes and within the designs themselves. The study emphasized the potential of support tools to engage with these influential factors and improve

design decisions [16]. Similarly, Arpetti et.al support for reflection, considering the educational needs of learners, ease of use, time efficiency, design reuse, and guidance in the design process were identified as crucial requirements by teachers [21]. The sharing of design practices was considered neutral, while software compatibility, graphical representation of designs, collaboration features, author identification, and aesthetics were found to be less important for teachers when it comes to learning design. Conole evaluated LD tools and identified support features such as flexibility, particularly in adapting designs to different educational contexts, was desirable and positively received by teachers. Support for the reuse and adaptation of designs was preferred over creating entirely new designs. Usability was consistently valued by teachers in various evaluation studies. The textual representation of designs was also appreciated by teachers when evaluating a tool [6]. In a systematic review conducted by Dagnino et al. identified categories of teachers' needs included flexibility for the reuse, revision, and adaptation of designs to educational needs, as well as support for the design process itself and providing guidance. The review also highlighted the importance of support for retrieving existing designs, facilitating cooperation among teachers through peer evaluation and collaborative editing, and supporting reflection through graphical or textual representation of designs. Other important factors included ease of use, textual & graphical representation, & activating design thinking processes aligned with teachers' familiarity and institutional design culture [22].

This literature review has identified various forms of support, including professional development, collaborative communities, mentoring, and access to resources. These studies collectively highlight the significance of various supports, such as knowledge enhancement, sharing practices, flexibility, ease of use, design reuse, and reflection, in assisting teachers with learning design processes and promoting effective educational practices. To understand the specific support required by Indian teachers in designing effective LDs, there is need to explore their experiences and perspectives. By addressing the support requirements of teachers, we can empower teachers to overcome barriers, leverage technology effectively, and create engaging and impactful learning designs for their students. This review of literature and analysis of LD tools helped us identify different supports. These categories of supports would be used to help our coding in the research studies within Indian contexts.

III. BACKGROUND: TEACHER PREPARATION AND TRAINING IN INDIA

In India, teacher preparation and training are managed by institutes like National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE), State Councils of Educational Research and Training (SCERTs), District Institutes of Education and Training (DIETs), and universities offering Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) and Master of Education (M.Ed.) programs that are responsible for policies and initiatives. These institutions are responsible for designing and implementing teacher training programs to equip educators with the necessary knowledge, skills and competencies required for effective teaching. NCTE is main governing and regulating body which is responsible for setting the standards and guidelines for teacher education programs in the country. The primary focus of teacher preparation in India is on developing pedagogical knowledge, subject content expertise, classroom management skills and competencies required for effective teaching. The training

programs aim to equip teachers with the necessary foundational knowledge and teaching strategies to effectively engage students in the learning process. The program covers various subjects related to education, including pedagogy, educational psychology, curriculum development, assessment and evaluation, classroom management, educational technology, and inclusive education etc. Students engage in both theoretical coursework and practical training. Theoretical coursework includes lectures, seminars, and discussions on educational theories, teaching methodologies, and relevant research. Practical training includes teaching practice in schools, where students gain hands-on experience in planning and delivering lessons, managing classrooms, and assessing student learning.

Teacher Professional Development (TPD) programs in India are managed by various organizations and entities, including government bodies, educational institutions such as SCERTs, DIETs, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and private entities. NCTE plays a significant role in setting guidelines and standards for teacher professional development in the country. In India, TPD programs are designed to enhance the knowledge, skills, and competencies of teachers to improve their instructional practices and keep up with emerging trends and challenges in education. TPD programs aim to support teachers in their professional growth and provide them with opportunities for continuous learning and development. These programs typically focus on pedagogical advancements, subject-specific updates, classroom management techniques, educational technology or digital tools training etc. TPD programs in India may be delivered through various modes, including workshops, seminars, conferences, online courses, and mentoring programs. The duration and intensity of these programs can vary, ranging from short-term workshops to long-term professional development courses.

The focus on incorporating technology effectively into teaching practices is often limited to a single course on educational technology, which may not adequately prepare teachers to leverage technology in a meaningful way across various subjects and instructional contexts. Also, there is often limited emphasis on LDs, which involve the deliberate planning and organization of instructional activities to optimize learning outcomes. The focus is more on teaching methods rather than designing learning experiences that cater to diverse student needs and promote active and meaningful engagement. This highlights a gap in the Teacher Preparation and TPD programs in India, so there is need to support teachers in developing teachers' understanding and application of LDs and leveraging technology for enhanced teaching and learning experiences. For this, we need to understand and identify the supports needed by Indian teachers for LDs.

IV. METHOD

The broad research question (RQ) addressed in this study was “*What supports do teachers need for designing effective LDs while integrating ICT in the classroom?*” To address this, this study employed exploratory sequential mixed method in which the initial phase typically involves collecting and analyzing qualitative data, followed by a quantitative phase. Creswell defines exploratory sequential mixed methods as a

research approach "in which the researcher begins with a qualitative exploration of a phenomenon and then uses the results to inform subsequent quantitative data collection" [23]. In our study, the qualitative phase aims to explore the support for LDs that Indian teachers require via in-depth interviews. We also conducted a quantitative phase study aimed at gathering empirical data on the kinds of support needed by teachers for LDs and identify the prominent or dominant one. Also, investigate if there are any significant differences in support needed by teachers for designing effective LDs according to their demographics & contextual variables.

V. QUALITATIVE STUDY

The qualitative phase aims to explore the support required by teachers in designing effective LDs. Details of this phase have been previously published [24]. Here we provide a summary of the study design and findings.

We selected teachers from different types of schools (government, government aided-private, and unaided-private) in Delhi via interviews. We conducted interviews via online mode with a total of 6 teachers (4 males, 2 female), consisting of 3 in-service teachers and 3 pre-service teachers. Each interview took approximately 1 hour. Participants' academic backgrounds spanned various disciplines, including sciences, social science, mathematics, and languages. Prior to the study, the majority of participants (5 out of 6) had not utilized any LD tools. Using thematic analysis [25], eight themes emerged which were categorized based on their similarities. The three categories emerged as: creation, contextualization, and collaboration as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. DETAILS OF CATEGORIES AND THEMES EMERGED FROM EMPHICAL EVIDENCES

Categories	Themes
1. Creation	<p>a) Templates : LDs pprovided with prompts that can be easily filled by teachers without specific technical skills.</p> <p>b) Basket of strategies: LDs must have sets/samples of lessons on the same topic with different strategies.</p> <p>c) Review/ Comparison mechanism: Existing LDs provided that help in building new learning designs or reviewing new designs.</p> <p>d) Reusability: provided LDs were readily understood, adapted and reused by teachers in their context.</p>
2. Contextualization	<p>e) Understanding students' needs: LDs must cater to the needs of the learners.</p> <p>f) Relatable examples/content in context: LDs must provide specific examples that are related to the context of the learners.</p>
3. Collaboration	<p>g) Expert/Mentor support: LDs must provide a mechanism for expert feedback.</p> <p>h) Peer-support: LDs were created with support of peers like collaborating to create new designs or to review designs of their peers.</p>

Through this qualitative approach, we gained valuable insights about the supports that teachers required to design student-centered LDs successfully. These findings have serve as a foundation for second phase of the study.

VI. QUANTITATIVE STUDY

Based on the qualitative study findings, we identified variables, developed instrument to measure the kinds of supports required by teachers for effective LDs, identify the prominent ones and generate hypothesis The RQs in the quantitative phase are:

RQ1.What kinds of supports do teachers need for designing effective LDs while integrating ICT in the classroom? Which kind is more dominant or prominent?

RQ2 What are the demographic and contextual variables that affect the LD support requirement of teachers?

A. Participants

The participants in this study were school teachers from various educational settings in Delhi, NCR, which were the schools sampled for the study. Snowball sampling techniques were used for selecting participants (school teachers). A total of 167 teachers volunteered to participate in this study.

B. Instrumentation

A Learning Design Support Questionnaire (LDSQ) was developed to collect data on support required by teachers in designing effective LDs based on the existing literature and theoretical frameworks. The questionnaire comprised 12 items to measure three kinds of support: creation, contextualization, and collaboration. Each item was rated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). In addition to the LDSQ, a demographic and context-related information section was included in the questionnaire to gather data on teachers' age, gender, teaching experience, highest educational qualifications, grade level taught, training in information and communication technologies (ICT), availability of resources (e.g., computer laboratory, internet access, computer access in school, computer access in the home.), type of school and use of ICT by the teachers.

To establish the content validity of a questionnaire, experts in the field of education and educational technology are involved in the review process. These experts possess specialized knowledge and expertise in the specific domain of the research topic. They identified items that were redundant, unclear, or irrelevant to the construct being measured. Experts also suggested additional items that enhance the content coverage of the questionnaire or provide alternative wording or response options. Researchers carefully considered the feedback and recommendations provided by the experts and made necessary revisions to the questionnaire based on their input. This iterative process of review and revision helped establish the content validity of the questionnaire, ensuring that it measures the intended construct accurately and comprehensively.

Data was collected from 30 teachers to establish reliability. Cronbach's alpha was used to test reliability, and the results revealed that the scales and sub-scales had acceptable internal consistency reliabilities. LDSQ is a self-reporting survey that measures a continuum of three kinds of support for LDs: Creation, Contextualization and Collaboration. This survey comprises 12 statements using a 5-point Likert scale with response options ranging from

"disagree strongly" to "agree strongly." It also consists of 12 items about demographics variables and for understanding the context of the teachers. The names of variables and the number of items are as follows: Creation (5 items, i.e. Q1, Q2, Q4, Q8, Q9); Contextualization (5 items, i.e. Q3, Q5, Q10, Q11, Q12) and collaboration (2 items, i.e. Q6, Q7) reported that the Cronbach alpha internal-consistency reliabilities ranged between .75-.82. The reliability of the overall LDSQ is established with Cronbach's alpha i.e. 0.9. The reliability of variables: creation (.779), contextualization (.753) and collaboration (.825). Sample questions included:

- A repository of lesson plans in my topic will help.
- A template that I can use to generate my lesson plan will help
- Support from a mentor while I create lesson plans will help.
- Access to multiple examples of activities for a given topic will help in lesson planning.

C. Data Collection

LDSQ with items on teachers' characteristics, context and supports required for LDs was distributed among teachers through various online modes, i.e. WhatsApp, Gmail, telegram etc. and asked them to share their friends, colleagues. Data collection was conducted through an online survey i.e. Google Form administered to the participants. The survey was distributed using online platforms, and participants were given a specified time frame to complete the questionnaire. To ensure anonymity and confidentiality, participants were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and used for research purposes only. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their voluntary participation and understanding of the study's objectives and procedures. The data collected were kept confidential and used solely for research purposes.

D. Data Analysis

Quantitative data analysis was conducted to examine the support requirements of teachers for designing effective LDs and investigate potential differences based on demographic and contextual factors. First, descriptive statistics were performed. Descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, were calculated to determine the overall level of support needed for each kinds of support (creation, contextualization, collaboration) required for designing effective LDs. Then, the Shapiro-Wilk test was done to test the normality of the data for it to qualify for parametric tests. The test results for the normality of our data ($p < .001$), thereby violating the normality assumption. Therefore, we used the skewness and kurtosis results between -1.0 and $+1.0$ and assumed the distribution to be sufficiently normal to qualify the data for a parametric test. The sample size was also significant. There, inferential statistics, such as t-tests and analysis of variance (ANOVA), were used to analyze the data and identify significant differences in LDs support requirements based on demographic and contextual variables. The quantitative study employed a well-designed questionnaire (LDSQ) to gather data on the support requirements of teachers in designing effective learning designs. The data analysis aimed to identify the kinds of support needed and explore potential differences based on teachers' demographics and contextual factors.

E. Quantitative Study Findings

Teacher demographics namely age, gender, teaching experience, highest educational qualifications, grade of teachers, subject taught, and context-related factors assessed in this study, namely, training in ICT, type of schools, availability of computer laboratory, internet access, computer access in school, computer access in the home and the use of ICT in the classroom. K-12 teachers were included in the sample, regardless of the number of years of teaching experience, subject-matter expertise, or other demographic variables (gender, age). Of the 200 teachers who received the surveys, 167 responded with usable returns.

1) Frequency distribution of demographics and context related data of participants(n=167)

TABLE II. FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF DEMOGRAPHICS VARIABLES OF PARTICIPANTS

Variables	Frequency	Mean	SD
Gender			
Male	52 (31.13%)	47.7	9.37
Female	115 (68.86%)	46.8	9.33
Age Group			
21-30	17 (10.17%)	48.4	8.75
31-40	73 (43.71%)	47.6	10.13
41-50	47 (28.14%)	46.6	8.83
51 -above	30 (17.96%)	46.0	8.57
Teaching Experience (in yrs)			
1-5	43 (25.74%)	47.3	9.21
6-10	37 (22.15%)	48.4	9.68
11-15	30 (17.96%)	45.9	11.52
16-20	21 (12.57%)	48	7.63
21-25	12 (7.18%)	48.4	7.42
25-above	24 (24.37%)	44.8	11.52
Educational Qualification			
UG+B.Ed.	33 (19.76%)	47.1	8.52
UG+B.Ed.+PG	106 (63.47%)	46.6	9.69
UG+B.Ed.+PG+M.Ed.	19 (11.37%)	48.6	8.78
D El Ed	9 (5.38%)	50.2	9.27
Teaching Grade Level			
PGT	31 (18.56%)	47.7	8.88
TGT	113 (67.66%)	46.5	9.36
PRT	22 (13.17%)	49.4	9.88
Subject Taught			
Science	28 (16.76%)	47.6	9.99
Langauge	54 (32.33%)	44.7	10.17
Social Science	34 (20.35%)	47.9	7.71
Mathematics	22 (13.17%)	48.1	8.51
Computer Science	8 (4.79%)	49.1	5.49
All	21 (12.57%)	49.5	10.72

Table 2 presents the frequency distribution and descriptive statistics of the demographics variables of the participants. It shows that out of the total (167) participants, 52 individuals (31.13%) identified as male, while 115 individuals (68.86%) identified as female in which majority belongs to 31-40 age range groups. The highest percentage of participants, 43 individuals (25.74%), falls within the 1-5 years of teaching

experience category. The highest percentage of participants, 106 individuals (63.47%), hold a UG+B.Ed.+PG qualification and majority (67.66%) were trained graduate teachers (TGT).

Table 3 presents the frequency distribution and descriptive statistics of the context-related data of the participants. Majority (58.08%) of the teachers have not attended any training or workshop related to ICT. Majority (97%) of teachers belong to government school. Majority (86.82%) of school have computer laboratory but not internet access. Majority of teachers have access of computer in home not at school. Still, 65.26% of teachers uses ICT in the classroom.

TABLE III. FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF CONTEXTUAL VARIABLES OF PARTICIPANTS

Variables	Frequency (%)	Mean	SD
ICT training/workshop			
No	97 (58.08%)	46.4	10.2
Yes	70 (41.92%)	48.1	7.98
School Type			
Govt. aided	3 (1.79%)	49	9.64
Govt.	162 (97.0%)	47.1	9.25
Private	2 (1.19%)	45	21.21
Computer Laboratory in School			
Yes	145 (86.82%)	47.6	9.22
No	22 (11.97%)	43.6	9.40
Internet Access			
Yes	65 (38.92%)	48.7	8.85
No	102 (61.07%)	46.1	9.52
Own Computer access in School			
Yes	42 (25.14%)	47.7	8.39
No	125 (74.85%)	46.9	9.64
Laptop/Computer access at home			
No	68 (40.71%)	45	10.5
Yes	99 (59.28%)	48.5	8.14
Use ICT in the classroom			
Yes	109 (65.26%)	48.6	8.60
No	58 (34.73%)	44.3	10

2) *Frequency distribution of demographics and context related data of participants of teachers' agreement scores on each items of LDSQ (n=167)*

Table 4 revealed that teachers require all three kinds of support in designing effective LDs i.e. creation, contextualization and collaboration. Teachers need creation support like Templates / Prompts that they can quickly fill without specific technical skills. A basket of strategies that consists of sets/samples of lessons on the same topic with different approaches. Comparison mechanism having sample LDs provided that help build new learning designs or review new designs reused by teachers were able to effectively adapt and reuse previously documented learning designs according to their own needs. Teachers need contextualization support, like learning designs must cater to the needs of the learners. Relatable examples/content in context: Learning designs must provide specific examples of the learners' context. Also, shows that out of three support teachers require contextualization related support more in designing effective LDs, followed by creation and collaboration.

3) *The result of significant differences between Learning Design Support and demographic & context related variables of teacher.*

To address RQ2. The following hypothesis was tested.

1. H0: There is no significant difference between support required by teachers for learning design and demographic variables namely age, gender, teaching experience, highest educational qualifications, grade of teachers, subject taught.
2. H0: There is no significant difference between support required by teachers for learning design and. Context related variables, namely, training in ICT, type of schools, availability of computer laboratory, internet access, computer access in school, computer access in the home and the use of ICT in the classroom.

Findings revealed that the demographic-related variables like gender ($p=.592$), age ($p=.756$), teaching experience ($p=.634$), highest educational qualifications ($p=.621$), grade of teachers ($p=.429$), and subject taught ($p=.390$), are not significantly different with Learning design support requirement of teachers. The following context-related factors like training in ICT ($p=.252$), type of schools ($p=.952$), availability of computer laboratory ($p=.058$), internet access ($p=.083$), computer access in school ($p=.621$) are not significant with Learning design support requirement of teachers. Apart from that, we found that there is a substantial difference between LDS and teachers who use ICT in the classroom($p=.004$) and have computer access at home ($p=.016$).

TABLE IV. THE FREQUENCY DISTRIUTON OF TEACHERS' AGREEMENT SCORES ON EACH ITEMS OF LDSQ

Teachers' agreement scores on each items of LDSQ.						
S. No.	Items	SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	A repository of lesson plans in my topic will help.	3 1.8%	13 7.8%	35 21%	55 32.9%	61 36.5%
2	I intend to use the lesson plans in the repository as is.	6 3.6%	13 7.8%	53 31.7%	64 38.3%	31 18.6%
3	I intend to revise and re-prepare the lesson plans in the repository.	3 1.8%	11 6.6%	41 24.6%	65 38.9%	47 28.1%
4	A template that I can use to generate my lesson plan will help.	2 1.2%	8 4.8%	41 24.6%	64 38.3%	52 31.1%
5	Access to multiple examples of activities for a given topic will help in lesson planning.	2 1.2%	3 1.8%	36 21.6%	52 31.1%	74 44.3%
6	Support from a mentor while I create lesson plans will help.	4 2.4%	6 3.6%	46 27.5%	62 37.1%	49 29.3%
7	Support from peers while I create lesson plans will help.	3 1.8%	6 3.6%	44 26.3%	58 34.7%	56 33.5%
8	Support in framing LOs will help me in lesson planning	1 6%	9 5.4%	40 24.0%	64 38.3%	53 31.7%
9	Support in framing assessment questions alignment with LOs will help me in lesson planning.	2 1.2%	6 3.6%	45 26.9%	58 34.7%	56 33.5%
10	Support in selection of appropriate Edtech tools for defined purposes will help me in lesson planning.	3 1.8%	7 4.2%	45 26.9%	61 36.5%	51 30.5%
11	Support in selection of appropriate Edtech tools for particular topics will help me in lesson planning.	3 1.8%	4 2.4%	44 26.3%	68 40.7%	48 28.7%
12	Sample lesson plans based on different strategies for the same topic will help in comparison.	1 0.6%	5 3.0%	36 21.6%	67 40.1%	58 34.7%

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The research conducted among teachers in Delhi, India revealed diverse areas of support needed by teachers to develop learner-centric LDs. Our findings indicate that teachers require substantial assistance in creating and contextualizing learning designs, as well as opportunities for effective collaboration in their development [25]. Also, shows that out of three supports, teachers require contextualization related support more in designing effective LDs, followed by creation and collaboration. These findings are consistent with prior studies examining the support teachers require when designing learning designs. For instance, Dagnino et. al. [22] research emphasizes the need for teachers to have access to pre-designed templates and flexibility in making pedagogical decisions while structuring learning designs. In our study, teachers demonstrated a willingness to receive support in conceptualizing and applying the learners' context. Similarly, the endeavor to familiarize oneself with students' backgrounds and characteristics is identified as a recurring theme in the research conducted by Bennett et al. [16].

There are several variables that can affect the learning design support requirements of teachers, including their level of experience, their subject matter expertise, their technological proficiency, their pedagogical content knowledge, and the context in which they are teaching. Research studies have explored the impact of these variables on teachers' learning design support requirements. In our study, we found that there is no significant difference between

support required by teachers for LDs creation and teaching experiences. In contrast to this, a study found that teachers with more experience tended to require less support in terms of designing effective learning while teachers with less experience needed more guidance and support [26].

In present study, we found that there is a statistically significant difference between teachers used and not used ICT in the classroom with the supports teachers required for LD. Our study found that there is a substantial difference between LDs and teachers who have computer access at home. A study found that teachers in schools with limited resources required more support in designing technology-enhanced learning activities than teachers in more affluent schools. In addition, the context in which teachers are teaching can also impact their learning design support requirements. Overall, the learning design support requirements of teachers are complex and multifaceted, and are influenced by a range of factors. Understanding these factors can help educational designers and policy makers provide appropriate support and resources to teachers to enhance their teaching practices.

Understanding the support requirements of teachers in learning design has significant implications for both practitioners and researchers. Practitioners can utilize this knowledge to develop targeted support programs and resources that address the specific needs of teachers. By providing teachers with the necessary support, educational institutions can enhance teaching quality, student engagement, and learning outcomes. For researchers, this study contributes

to the existing literature on learning design supports. It provides insights into the specific support requirements of teachers and highlights areas that warrant further investigation. Future research can delve deeper into the effectiveness of different forms of support, explore the impact of contextual factors on support requirements, and identify innovative approaches to support teachers in designing effective learning experiences.

Furthermore, this study contributes to the broader conversation on educational innovation, as it explores the intersection of pedagogy, technology, and teacher support in the digital era. Moving forward, further research and the development of targeted support interventions are necessary to bridge the gap between theory and practice in learning design support. This research will contribute to the growing body of knowledge surrounding learning design practices and help bridge the gap between theory and practice in educational settings. These findings have served as a foundation for future research and the development of practical strategies to enhance teacher support in learning design practices.

In conclusion, supporting teachers in designing effective learning designs is crucial for harnessing the potential of technology and promoting student-centered learning. Understanding and addressing the support requirements of teachers can empower teachers and lead to enhanced learning experiences for students.

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